

What do the competitiveness indicators tell us about economic performance?

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Abstract: This paper presents an extensive statistical investigation of the relationship between economic performance and the Global Competitiveness Index as a possible predictor of economic development. The analysis is based on a large sample of countries at various levels of economic development. Various measures of both competitiveness indicators based on the data published by the World Economic Forum and economic performance indicators are employed. The results obtained from the panel analysis show that, on average, the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness indicators is weak. However, when we differentiate among the economies according to their economic level we can identify some statistically significant relationships between economic performance and certain measures of competitiveness. The results show that in many cases the probability of inferring systematically wrong expectations about the economic performance given the information contained in the competitiveness indices is high.

JEL Classifications: O11, O50, O57

Keywords: Business cycle, economic growth, economic performance, panel GMM, WEF competitiveness indicators

Citation: Pošta, V., Nečadová, M. (2019). What do the competitiveness indicators tell us about economic performance?. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 15(5), 593-607.

1. Introduction

The country competitiveness indicators published by the World Economic Forum (WEF) have gained popularity, however, the answer to the question as to what extent they supply useful information with respect to the analysis of determinants of macroeconomic growth remains unanswered. As we show below, the empirical research which tackles this question is relatively scarce. The second problem is that most of the contributions are rather old and based on very limited data sets, which significantly constrained the methods which could be used to assess the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness indicators.

Our main contribution is to present an extensive econometrical investigation of the question of the relationship between economic performance and information contained in the competitiveness indices published by the World Economic Forum.

For this purpose, we use as much data as we can regarding both the number of economies and time span. Given a large number of cross-sections and still relatively limited time dimensions we suppose the most convenient way to analyze the data at this point is dynamic panel analysis based on Arellano-Bond estimator.

We show that the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness indices is generally weak. In our opinion, the most important findings are that the

relevance of this relationship is strongly dependent on the economic level of the analyzed economy. We also show that it is possible that the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness indicators may be conditioned by the state of the business cycle, however, given the data we have, we are not able to investigate this indication properly.

Indeed the evaluation of the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness indicators has its merit from the point of view of macroeconomic analysis, however, we suppose that it also brings some important findings with respect to business and investment analysis. The information published by the WEF is well known, frequently cited and it is an integral part of the common economic information which enters economic decision-making on many levels. This analysis helps to attach relevant value to this particular information.

The paper is structured as follows: in the following part we present key information on the concept of competitiveness, the WEF competitiveness indicators and findings related to the relationship between the WEF competitiveness indicators and economic performance; in the third part of the paper we present the data and the approach we took to examine the relationship in question; in the fourth part we present the results, and, finally, we summarize the findings.

2. The WEF competitiveness indicators and their relation to economic performance

The never-ending competitiveness debate starts from the differences between macro and micro-level aspects of this phenomenon. In a microeconomic sense, the term is fairly straightforward. A standard definition would be that competitiveness refers to the capacity of a firm to compete, grow, and be profitable in the relevant market. In the macroeconomic context, the term national competitiveness began to be applied in the 1980s concerning the change of the nature of international trade relations. The macroeconomic use of the term is often not clearly defined. We understand the assessment of countries according to their competitiveness as a way to evaluate their future economic potential and opportunities for further development and growth.

Buckley et al. (1988) summarize the relevant measures of international competitiveness. They recommend differentiating three dimensions: performance, potential, and management process. They also make a distinction between four levels of analysis: country, industry, firm, and product. Delgado et al. (2012) accentuate three ideas connected with the evolution of the competitiveness debate: market share, costs, and productivity. High market shares can be a symptom of underlying location advantages, however, the same result can be achieved through targeted and distortive subsidies as well. They emphasize that the naive interpretation of competitiveness as low costs is misguided if prosperity is the policy's objective. Camagni (2002) also supports the territory approach to the judgment of competitiveness.

Some well-known objections to the term in question come from Krugman (1994, 1996), Reinert (1994), Cho & Moon (2005, 2013), who consider the concept of macroeconomic competitiveness elusive and misleading. Cho & Moon (2005, 2013) and Lall (2001) focus on the well-known approach developed by Porter (1990), which is based on the so-called diamond of national advantage consisting in the interlinkages between four pillars: firm

strategy, structure and rivalry; factor conditions; demand conditions; and related and supporting industries.

Moving on to the concept of competitiveness on which we build the technical analysis, Trabold (1995) and Berger & Bristow (2009) discuss four aspects of national competitiveness: the ability to sell (costs and trade performance), the ability to earn (productivity and performance orientation), the ability to adjust (innovation and flexibility), and the ability to attract (place attractiveness). Fagerberg et al. (2007) deem the same aspects of competitiveness necessary, accept Krugman's critical remarks and seek relevant indicators for four factors of economic performance: technology competitiveness, capacity competitiveness, price competitiveness, and demand competitiveness. They aim to overcome the lack of traditional attitude, which is the focus mainly on price and cost comparisons. Their analysis based on statistical data can be regarded as an alternative to the traditional approach which is primarily concerned with the potentially damaging effects of excessive wage growth on the economy.

All aspects of competitiveness mentioned above are taken into account in the well-known international competitiveness rankings: the World Competitiveness Yearbook and the Global Competitiveness Report. These rankings point out the role of productivity and the capacities of countries to compete in the world markets to improve their economic performance and standards of living. The resulting competitiveness indicator is constructed as a multidimensional composite indicator. The declared aim of the composite indicator is to be a comprehensive evaluation of national competitiveness for a heterogeneous group of countries with different characteristics and on various stages of development. This proposition raises frequent critical objections to the methodology of these rankings. According to Cho & Moon (2005, 2013) and Lall (2001), a comparison of national competitiveness is more meaningful when the nations are endowed with similar comparative advantages, they are on a similar level of development, and they compete in similar industries. Lall (2001, p.1505) emphasizes the necessity of two prerequisites for a sound measurement of national competitiveness: it must confine itself to activities involving competition between nations, otherwise, it becomes a very different exercise dealing in fact with productivity or growth, and it must revolve around market failures that affect competitive ability, particularly the evolution of dynamic comparative advantage.

As Freudenberg (2003, p.5) remarks: composite indices have a lot of methodological difficulties that must be confronted and can be easily manipulated to produce desired outcomes. The main pros and cons of using composite indicators have been widely debated. The discussion is summarized by Saisana & Tarantola (2002). Saisana et al. (2005) recommend the use of uncertainty and sensitivity analysis to acquire useful insights during the process of building composite indicators. This methodology is accepted by Saltelli (2007), who, on the example of the Lisbon Strategy, explores the extent to which composite indicators can fulfill the task of underpinning the development of data-based narratives for political advocacy.

The Global Competitiveness Report (GCR) is published annually by the World Economic Forum (WEF). This annual competitiveness report is based mostly on soft data, which allows a larger number of countries to be monitored than in the case of the World Competitiveness Yearbook published by the International Institute for Management Development. The Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) of a country is computed as a weighted average of 12 pillars: institutions, infrastructure, macroeconomic environment,

health and primary education, higher education and training, goods market efficiency, labor market efficiency, financial market development, technological readiness, market size, business sophistication, and innovation. The first five pillars are also referred to as basic requirements, the second five pillars are designated as efficiency enhancers and the last two pillars are known as innovation and sophistication factors. The weights of the pillars depend on the stage of development of the particular economy.

According to Ochel & Röhn (2006), the omission of growth factors should contribute to the low explanatory power of the GCI for economic growth.

Freudenberg (2003), Ochel & Röhn (2006), Lall (2001), Perez Moreno et al. (2016) point out that the choice of the methods of standardization, normalization as well as the weighting of the pillars has an impact on country rankings.

Moving further on to discuss the relationship between the competitiveness and economic performance, the WEF used simple correlation and a bivariate model, in which they regress the log of the level of GDP per capita on the GCI score, to test the validity of the GCI as a predictor of the level of productivity. These results may be found in The Global Competitiveness Report 2010-11, 2014-15, and the edition 2016-17. The WEF also checks the relationship between the GCI and the growth rate of a country with the result of a significant relationship. They also take account of the conditional convergence effect; a natural tendency for poor economies to grow faster.

Some empirical investigation of the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness based on the WEF data may be found in Porter (2003), Porter et al. (2006) and Porter et al. (2007), however, the simple panel regression used in these analyses, which was chosen for the lack of data, could not meet the required assumptions. This is indicated by the tests we present below. Porter et al. (2007) show that the explanatory power of competitiveness indicators increases with the level of economic development of the countries, which is a result we confirm below.

Concerning the results presented below, Delgado et al. (2012) show that country heterogeneity, approximated by country fixed effects in terms of geography, endowments, and historical institutions, decreases the regression coefficient of the indicator of microeconomic competitiveness in their regression model. The explanation of performance differences among countries based on historical institution variables follows up on Acemoglu et al. (2001, 2003).

The robustness of the WEF methodology was checked in the Global Competitiveness Report 2010-11. According to Nardo & Annoni (2010), the analysis confirms the GCI structure, but for some pillars, the analysis suggests redundancy in the sub pillar division. In addition to this result, some indicators were found to be statistically unrelated to the rest of the indicators in the pillar. This fact can indicate that this indicator might describe a different aspect of competitiveness than the other indicators included in the pillar.

Ochel & Röhn (2006), Berger & Bristow (2009), Lall (2001) dispute this WEF tests of robustness and the focus on correlation instead of causation. These authors identify the problem of circular reasoning and causation.

In the edition of the GCR 2016-17, the analysis shows that GDP per capita has become more closely correlated with the technological readiness, business sophistication, and innovation pillars than with the infrastructure, health and primary education, and market-related pillars. According to Sala-I-Martin et al. (2016), these results illustrate how sources

of productivity within firms are playing a larger role than investment in basic physical and human capital.

3. Data and econometrical approach

We verify the relationship between the economic performance and the competitiveness index on the sample of the WEF data.

The original sample contains 152 countries differentiated according to their economic status into four categories: high income, upper-middle-income, lower-middle-income, and lower-income countries. Given the data on economic performance and competitiveness index, this initial sample was reduced to 118 countries, which are listed in Appendix A. This was because the indicator of economic performance (GDP per capita, GDP per person employed or the competitiveness indicator, see further below) was not available at various points in time for the remaining 34 countries. The sample was further reduced by four countries in the third estimation which uses gross national income per capita as an indicator of economic performance due to the lack of data. This information is specified in Appendix A. Going back to the sample of 118 countries, the tables in Appendix A show that 47 of them were high income, 30 - upper middle income, 28 - lower middle income, and 13 - low income.

The basic yearly time sample run from 2006 to 2017. This sample is adjusted given the needs of the particular model. This is indicated in the presentation of the estimates.

We use three measures of economic performance: gross domestic product per capita in purchasing power parity referred to as GDP/capita, gross domestic product per person employed in purchasing power parity referred to as GDP/empl, and gross national income per capita in purchasing power parity referred to as GNI/capita. The data come from GCI Dataset published by WEF and World Bank database named World Development Indicators. We used Levin-Lin-Chu unit root test to examine the presence of common unit root in the data, and as economic performance series in levels typically show, the data was found non-stationary.

To examine the relationship between economic performance and competitiveness index, we make use of 6 indicators:

- global competitiveness index GCI
- simple average of the respective pillars denoted as GCIA
- simple average of three subindices, more precisely, of basic requirements, efficiency enhancers, and innovation and sophistication factors denoted as GCIAA
- subindex of basic requirements denoted as GCIBR
- subindex of efficiency enhancers denoted as GCIEE
- subindex of innovation and sophistication factors denoted as GCIF

The stationarity of the competitiveness indices was once more checked by Levin-Lin-Chu unit root test and the series were found stationary. The performance indicators were stationarized by logarithmic differences.

The idea of how to examine the relationship between the competitiveness indicators on one hand and the performance indicators on the other hand rested on the inclusion of the performance indicators as explanatory variables in autoregressive processes of order 1 for the performance indicators. To take account of possible endogeneity effects and also of

the limited time dimension of the data with respect to a relatively large number of cross-sections we make use of a generalized method of moments approach based on Arellano-Bond estimator.

The instruments used are the second lag of the performance indicator and the first lag of the competitiveness indicator. The validity of instruments was tested by Sargan-Hansen J-test, which is reported in Tables 1 - 5. White standard errors, i.e. heteroskedasticity-consistent standard errors, were used. Autocorrelation in the residuals was tested by the Arellano-Bond test for the first two lags. Given the fact that the model is estimated in first differences, the Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) shows possible autoregression in the first differences of the residuals. This is confirmed in many of the cases and is also expected. The more important is the test for the AR(2) autoregression, which indicates whether or not there is autoregression in the levels of the residuals. These results are also reported in Tables 1 - 5.

4. Analysis of the results

The output of the estimations is given in Tables 1 - 5 in Appendix B.

On the level of the whole sample, Table 1, some statistically significant relationships were found between all three measures of economic performance and the competitiveness indicator as a whole (GCI) and also the subindex of the basic requirements (GCIBR). A large number of statistically significant negative coefficients for the other measures of competitiveness might be explained by the specific period in question. The mean growth of GDP per capita was 0.020 with a standard deviation of 0.041, which means that many countries in the sample experienced declines in economic performance indicators.

The results for the high-income countries, Table 2, show a general picture of strong positive relationships between the three measures of economic performance on one hand and the set of competitiveness indicators on the other hand. The results are generally less significant for GDP per person employed as a measure of economic performance and the relationship between economic performance and the subindex of efficiency enhancers (GCIEE) is negative. This might be due to the fact that while the mean growth of GDP per capita was slightly positive, 0.009, the situation especially on labor markets and financial markets was deteriorating in many years of the sample. Let us recall that labor market efficiency and financial market development enter this subindex of GCI.

Table 3 which reports results for the upper-middle income countries shows very poor results as compared with the expectations of a positive relationship between economic performance and competitiveness. The only statistically significant relationship of the expected sign was identified between GNI per capita and the subindex of basic requirements (GCIBR). This segment of economies experienced a mean growth of 0.027, which given GNI per capita as a measure of economic performance, is reasonably explained only by autoregression, and only in the one case also by a competitiveness indicator.

The lower-middle income countries, whose results are reported in Table 4, experienced a mean growth of GDP per capita even higher, 0.034, and generally this growth may be explained to a significant degree by the competitiveness indicators as the autoregression of the performance indicators is negative.

The last reported results for low-income countries in Table 5 show a picture that runs quite contrary to the previous case. The growth of economic performance, a mean growth of GDP per capita of 0.023, is explained by autoregression with the exception of the subindex of sophistication and innovation factors (GCIIF).

Given the results, it may be readily deduced that the strongest relationships between economic performance and competitiveness are to be expected in the segments of high income and lower-middle countries, on the other hand, the expected positive relationship between the two seems highly uncertain in the segments of upper-middle and low-income countries.

Aiginger & Vogel (2015) define a broad measure of competitiveness which exceeds the sole measure of economic performance as measured by GDP by including measures of social inclusion and environmental sustainability. They show that factors such as wages, productivity, and unit labor costs, which they denote as price factors, bear no explanatory value for such a measure of competitiveness. The low effect of price competitiveness was also reported by Fagerberg et al. (2007) on a much larger sample of countries. This might be viewed as contradictory to the results presented here, as the subindex of basic requirements which also includes these so-called price measures proved many times statistically significant. However, they test the relationship on only high-income countries, EU, and this analysis indeed does not regard performance in the broader view as they do.

Bouis et al. (2011) perform a long-run analysis on a sample of OECD and other countries, which means that not only high-income countries were included in the sample. Their results show that with GDP per employment as a measure of economic performance, education policy and barriers to entrepreneurship also play an important role besides the traditional long-run growth factors, which are stock of physical capital and human capital. From the point of GCI view, this means that the subindices of basic requirements and efficiency enhancers should be found significant, the former containing, among others, health and primary education and higher education and training, and the second accounting for, among others, goods market efficiency and market size. Let us recall that it was the subindex of basic requirements which along with the whole GCI was found to be a statistically significant explanatory variable of economic performance for the whole sample, Table 1, and it was the only statistically significant measure of competitiveness in explaining performance measured by GNI per capita in the case of upper-middle income countries, Table 3. On the other hand, it is somewhat puzzling that efficiency enhancers were the only measure of competitiveness with a negative estimated influence on economic performance in the case of high-income countries, Table 2.

Delgado et al. (2012) identified a positive relationship between economic performance and social infrastructure, political institutions, monetary and fiscal policy, and microeconomic environment. They used a broad sample of countries, however, the time sample was as in our case rather limited, 2001 - 2008, and thus it was heavily influenced by the growth of the world economy at that time.

5. Conclusions

We showed that on average the relationship between the economic performance and competitiveness indicators is weak. On the other hand, differentiating among the economies concerning their economic level helps to identify statistically significant

relationships and thus goes to show that in many individual cases solid relationship between the economic performance and competitiveness may and should be expected.

More specifically, in the case of high income and lower-middle-income countries, strong relationships were found between the competitiveness indicators and measures of economic performance in the form of GDP and GNI. On the other hand, generally poor relationships between economic performance and competitiveness measures should be expected in the case of upper-middle-income and low-income countries. Looking at upper-middle-income countries and the fact that in many cases the growth of their economies is still based on resource exploitation or low-paid labor manufacturing the results are not so surprising.

While the results of our analysis are not directly comparable with other papers and certainly are influenced by the fact that a significant portion of the sample covered the period of the aftermath of the financial crisis, we also showed that in some aspects they are not at odds with similar research.

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Appendix A

TABLE 1. HIGH INCOME COUNTRIES.

CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY
AUS	Australia	FRA	France	LVA	Latvia	SGP	Singapore
AUT	Austria	DEU	Germany	LTU	Lithuania	SVK	Slovak Rep.
BHR	Bahrain	GRC	Greece	LUX	Luxembourg	SVN	Slovenia
BEL	Belgium	HKG	Hong Kong	MLT	Malta	ESP	Spain
CAN	Canada	HUN	Hungary	NLD	Netherlands	SWE	Sweden
CHL	Chile	ISL	Iceland	NZL	New Zealand	CHE	Switzerland
HRV	Croatia	IRL	Ireland	NOR	Norway	TTO	Trinidad & T.
CYP	Cyprus	ISR	Israel	OMN	Oman	ARE	United Arab E.
CZE	Czech Rep.	ITA	Italy	POL	Poland	GBR	United King.
DNK	Denmark	JPN	Japan	PRT	Portugal	USA	United States
EST	Estonia	KOR	Korea, Rep.	QAT	Qatar	URY	Uruguay
FIN	Finland	KWT	Kuwait	SAU	Saudi Arabia		

Source: Own construction.

Notes: 47 countries; LUX and SAU do not enter the estimates of the models for GNI/capita due to missing data on GNI.

TABLE 2. UPPER MIDDLE INCOME COUNTRIES

CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY
ALB	Albania	DOM	Dominican Republic	NAM	Namibia
DZA	Algeria	JAM	Jamaica	PAN	Panama
ARG	Argentina	JOR	Jordan	PER	Peru
AZE	Azerbaijan	KAZ	Kazakhstan	ROU	Romania
BWA	Botswana	LBN	Lebanon	RUS	Russian Federation
BRA	Brazil	MKD	Macedonia, FYR	SRB	Serbia
BGR	Bulgaria	MYS	Malaysia	ZAF	South Africa
CHN	China	MUS	Mauritius	THA	Thailand
COL	Colombia	MEX	Mexico	TUR	Turkey
CRI	Costa Rica	MNE	Montenegro	VEN	Venezuela

Source: Own construction.

Notes: 30 countries.

TABLE 3. LOWER MIDDLE INCOME COUNTRIES

CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY
ARM	Armenia	HND	Honduras	NGA	Nigeria
BGD	Bangladesh	IND	India	PAK	Pakistan
BOL	Bolivia	IDN	Indonesia	PRY	Paraguay
KHM	Cambodia	KEN	Kenya	PHL	Philippines
CMR	Cameroon	KGZ	Kyrgyz Republic	LKA	Sri Lanka
EGY	Egypt	LSO	Lesotho	UKR	Ukraine
SLV	El Salvador	MRT	Mauritania	VNM	Vietnam
GEO	Georgia	MNG	Mongolia	ZMB	Zambia
GHA	Ghana	MAR	Morocco		
GTM	Guatemala	NIC	Nicaragua		

Source: Own construction.

Notes: 28 countries; LSO, ZMB do not enter the estimates of the models for GNI/capita due to missing data on GNI.

TABLE 4. LOW INCOME COUNTRIES

CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY	CODE	COUNTRY
BDI	Burundi	MWI	Malawi	TZA	Tanzania
TCD	Chad	MLI	Mali	UGA	Uganda
ETH	Ethiopia	MOZ	Mozambique	ZWE	Zimbabwe
GMB	Gambia	NPL	Nepal		
MGD	Madagascar	SEN	Senegal		

Source: Own construction.

Notes: 13 countries.

Appendix B

TABLE 1. PANEL REGRESSIONS FOR THE WHOLE SAMPLE

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	118	118	118	118	118	118
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita
Dependent (-1)	0.10**	0.08**	0.09**	0.26***	-0.01	0.19***
Comp. ind.	0.02**	-0.04	-0.06	0.14***	-0.31*	-0.07**
J-statistic	2.03	4.22	4.20	3.91	3.66	3.70
AR(1)	-1.91*	-2.52**	-2.88**	-3.56***	-3.31***	-2.55**
AR(2)	-1.37	-2.24*	-2.06*	-1.55	2.01*	-1.78*

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	118	118	118	118	118	118
Time sample	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016
Dependent	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl
Dependent (-1)	0.08*	0.02	0.03	0.14**	0.04	0.11**
Comp. ind.	0.08***	-0.01	-0.03	0.13***	-0.18**	-0.03
J-statistic	3.01	3.39	3.45	2.80	2.85	3.12
AR(1)	-3.59***	-2.45**	-2.45**	-3.48***	-2.37**	-2.49**
AR(2)	-1.51	-1.72*	-1.61	-1.12	-0.82	-0.56

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	114	114	114	114	114	114
Time sample	2008:2017	2008:2017	2008:2017	2008:2017	2008:2017	2008:2017
Dependent	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita
Dependent (-1)	0.13***	0.12***	0.11***	0.24***	0.02	0.11***
Comp. ind.	0.22***	-0.06	-0.05	0.33***	-0.32***	-0.02
J-statistic	3.41	3.55	3.49	2.32	3.52	3.61
AR(1)	-3.52***	-3.55***	-2.53**	-2.46**	-2.35**	-3.25***
AR(2)	-1.83*	-2.01**	-1.96**	-1.57	-0.68	-1.32

Source: Own estimates.

Notes: The competitiveness indicators GCI, GCIA, GCIAA, GCIBR, GCIEE, GCIIF, and the performance indicators gdp/capita, gdp/empl, and gni/capita are explained in Part 3. Comp. ind. refers to the competitiveness indicator used as an explanatory variable in the particular regression; this is given by the indicator used to name each model. Instruments: constant, one lag of competitiveness indicators, second lag of GDP growth. J-statistic refers to the test of the validity of over-identifying restrictions with the null of the restrictions being valid. AR(1) and AR(2) refer to m-statistic of autocorrelation test in residuals with the null of no autocorrelation. *, **, *** means rejection of the null at 10%, 5%, and 1% level of significance, respectively.

TABLE 2. PANEL REGRESSIONS FOR THE HIGH INCOME COUNTRIES

Model	GCI	GCI A	GCI A A	GCI B R	GCI E E	GCI I F
Cross-section	47	47	47	47	47	47
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita
Dependent (-1)	0.11***	0.13***	0.13***	0.10***	0.19***	0.13***
Comp. ind.	0.18***	0.14***	0.13***	0.27***	-0.05***	0.11***
J-statistic	30.26	33.39	33.69	32.40	38.56*	35.55
AR(1)	-3.31***	-2.42**	-2.28**	-2.57**	-3.36***	-2.56**
AR(2)	-1.20	-1.08	-1.44	-1.21	-1.60	-1.73*

Model	GCI	GCI A	GCI A A	GCI B R	GCI E E	GCI I F
Cross-section	47	47	47	47	47	47
Time sample	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016
Dependent	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl
Dependent (-1)	0.16***	0.18***	0.22***	0.06	0.24***	0.17***
Comp. ind.	0.07***	0.03**	0.01	0.20***	-0.06***	0.03**
J-statistic	27.11	28.13	29.41	27.72	24.04	24.01
AR(1)	-3.60***	-3.58***	-2.47**	-2.33**	-2.46**	-3.37***
AR(2)	-1.37	-1.29	-1.19	-1.53	-0.38	-1.47

Model	GCI	GCI A	GCI A A	GCI B R	GCI E E	GCI I F
Cross-section	45	45	45	45	45	45
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita
Dependent (-1)	0.12***	0.16***	0.15***	0.15***	0.22***	0.19***
Comp. ind.	0.11***	0.07***	0.06***	0.20***	-0.07***	0.03***
J-statistic	29.33	24.34	31.55*	30.51	30.65	25.25
AR(1)	-3.55***	-2.45**	-3.51***	-2.31**	-2.35**	-2.47**
AR(2)	-1.34	-1.25	-1.41	-0.57	-0.44	-1.27

Source: Own estimates.

Notes: The competitiveness indicators GCI, GCI A, GCI A A, GCI B R, GCI E E, GCI I F, and the performance indicators gdp/capita, gdp/empl, and gni/capita are explained in Part 3. Comp. ind. refers to the competitiveness indicator used as an explanatory variable in the particular regression; this is given by the indicator used to name each model. Instruments: constant, one lag of competitiveness indicators, second lag of GDP growth. J-statistic refers to the test of the validity of over-identifying restrictions with the null of the restrictions being valid. AR(1) and AR(2) refer to m-statistic of autocorrelation test in residuals with the null of no autocorrelation. *, **, *** means rejection of the null at 10%, 5%, and 1% level of significance, respectively.

TABLE 3. PANEL REGRESSIONS FOR THE UPPER MIDDLE INCOME COUNTRIES

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	30	30	30	30	30	30
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita
Dependent (-1)	-0.02***	-0.02***	-0.01	0.05***	-0.03***	0.07***
Comp. ind.	-0.04***	-0.08***	-0.07***	-0.04***	-0.14***	-0.06***
J-statistic	28.06	29.41	29.44	29.67	29.01	28.28
AR(1)	-3.33***	-3.32***	-2.33**	-2.31**	-2.31**	-2.33**
AR(2)	-1.19	-1.31	-1.32	-1.29	-1.89*	-1.58

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	30	30	30	30	30	30
Time sample	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016
Dependent	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl
Dependent (-1)	-0.10***	-0.11***	-0.13***	-0.11***	-0.16***	-0.08***
Comp. ind.	-0.06***	-0.10***	-0.09***	-0.00	-0.17***	-0.04***
J-statistic	22.57	22.82	23.12	23.03	18.77	22.50
AR(1)	-2.78**	-3.62***	-3.25***	-2.31**	-3.24***	-3.77***
AR(2)	-1.26	-1.76*	-1.80*	-1.11	-1.95*	-1.55

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	30	30	30	30	30	30
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita
Dependent (-1)	0.05**	0.04***	0.04***	0.10***	0.03***	0.08***
Comp. ind.	-0.02**	-0.07***	-0.06***	0.05***	-0.11***	-0.06***
J-statistic	28.65	28.90	28.98	26.17	27.38	28.92
AR(1)	-3.55***	-2.71**	-3.73***	-2.42**	-2.51**	-2.63**
AR(2)	-1.70*	-1.62	-1.85*	-1.21	-1.80*	-1.73*

Source: Own estimates.

Notes: The competitiveness indicators GCI, GCIA, GCIAA, GCIBR, GCIEE, GCIIF, and the performance indicators gdp/capita, gdp/empl, and gni/capita are explained in Part 3. Comp. ind. refers to the competitiveness indicator used as an explanatory variable in the particular regression; this is given by the indicator used to name each model. Instruments: constant, one lag of competitiveness indicators, second lag of GDP growth. J-statistic refers to the test of the validity of over-identifying restrictions with the null of the restrictions being valid. AR(1) and AR(2) refer to m-statistic of autocorrelation test in residuals with the null of no autocorrelation. *, **, *** means rejection of the null at 10%, 5%, and 1% level of significance, respectively.

TABLE 4. PANEL REGRESSIONS FOR THE LOWER MIDDLE INCOME COUNTRIES

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	28	28	28	28	28	28
Time sample	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016
Dependent	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita	gdp/capita
Dependent (-1)	-0.05***	-0.06***	-0.03***	-0.04***	-0.04***	-0.03***
Comp. ind.	0.12***	0.09***	0.07***	0.09***	0.07***	-0.00
J-statistic	23.51	22.67	23.91	23.98	22.45	21.82
AR(1)	-2.37**	-2.35**	-2.33**	-2.32**	-3.35***	-2.31**
AR(2)	-1.58	-1.63*	-1.76*	-1.45	-1.51	-1.60

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	28	28	28	28	28	28
Time sample	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016	2009:2016
Dependent	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl	gdp/empl
Dependent (-1)	-0.05***	-0.07***	-0.08***	-0.06***	-0.06***	-0.06***
Comp. ind.	0.12***	0.11***	0.11***	0.09***	0.10***	0.05***
J-statistic	20.12	20.39	19.75	22.93	21.90	22.11
AR(1)	-3.36***	-2.30**	-2.31**	-2.24**	-3.32***	-2.62**
AR(2)	-1.44	-1.56	-1.47	-1.25	-1.61	-1.56

Model	GCI	GCIA	GCIAA	GCIBR	GCIEE	GCIIF
Cross-section	26	26	26	26	26	26
Time sample	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017	2009:2017
Dependent	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita	gni/capita
Dependent (-1)	-0.01***	-0.02***	-0.02***	-0.01***	-0.02***	-0.01***
Comp. ind.	0.11***	0.10***	0.10***	0.08***	0.04***	0.04***
J-statistic	25.32	24.80	25.39	25.33	25.45	25.53
AR(1)	-2.20**	-2.19**	-2.26**	-2.20**	-2.25**	-2.17**
AR(2)	-1.59	-1.58	-1.47	-1.35	-1.66	-1.60

Source: Own estimates.

Notes: The competitiveness indicators GCI, GCIA, GCIAA, GCIBR, GCIEE, GCIIF, and the performance indicators gdp/capita, gdp/empl, and gni/capita are explained in Part 3. Comp. ind. refers to the competitiveness indicator used as an explanatory variable in the particular regression; this is given by the indicator used to name each model. Instruments: constant, one lag of competitiveness indicators, second lag of GDP growth. J-statistic refers to the test of the validity of over-identifying restrictions with the null of the restrictions being valid. AR(1) and AR(2) refer to m-statistic of autocorrelation test in residuals with the null of no autocorrelation. *, **, *** means rejection of the null at 10%, 5%, and 1% level of significance, respectively.